

Synthesis and *in vitro* Serotonin-3-antagonist Activities of some Newer 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-thiones

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Among the four principal classes of 5HT receptors¹ (5HT₁, 5HT₂, 5HT₃ and 5HT₄), recent attention has been focussed on 5HT₃ receptor subtype area. Several 5HT₃ receptor antagonists, such as tropisetron (ICS 205-930)², ondasetron (GR 38032)³, granisetron (BRL 43694)⁴ and zatosetron (LY 277359)⁵ have already been effective in control of cancer chemotherapy-induced emesis^{6,7}. In addition, evidence has been presented for therapeutic role of this class of compounds⁸. Most of the reported 5HT₃ antagonists are amides or esters containing an end-nitrogen system which is often tertiary in nature. But these compounds being susceptible to hydrolysis are quite often not much of utility when it comes to *in vivo* administration. This compound character may be avoided by incorporation of H-bond accepters within a non-hydrolysable five-membered hetero-aromatic ring like 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety. In continuation of our earlier work with various aryl, aryl-alkyl and hetroaryl amides⁹ as well as esters¹⁰, this study reports the synthesis of some newer aryl and aryl-alkyl 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (Scheme 1) and their *in vitro* pharmacological evaluation as 5HT₃ receptor antagonist.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) CH₃OH, H₂SO₄, (ii) NH₂NH₂·H₂O and (iii) CS₂/NaOH, CH₃OH.

Results and Discussion

The key intermediates in this route for 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were the corresponding acid hydrazides (2a-g). These hydrazides were readily available by esterification of mother acids (1a-g) followed by reactions with hydrazine hydrate in methanol. The hydrazides were then converted into 1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (3a-g) by methanolic carbondisulphide under basic conditions.

All the oxadiazoles were screened for their 5HT₃ antagonism activity in guinea pig ileum studies⁷. Zatosetron maleate (LY 277359) was taken as a standard drug. Longitudinal section of illeal smooth muscle (2–3 cm) from healthy male guinea pig (200–400 g, Charles River) was mounted in organbath containing 40 ml of modified Krebs solution¹¹ with continuous aeration and temperature controlled at 37 ± 2°. Each tissue was placed under optimum resting force and allowed to equilibrate for 45 min before exposure to drugs. Isometric tissue contraction against bath concentration of 0.04 μg ml⁻¹ of 2-methylserotonin (agonist)² was recorded in presence of vehicle alone and 0.8 μg ml⁻¹ bath concentration of each antagonist (standard and synthetic compounds). Among the compounds tested 3a, 3b and 3g showed better activity than 3c-f, though all the compounds showed less activity as compared to that of zatosetron maleate. Further evaluations both in this model and in other well accepted 5HT₃ antagonist testing models, are now in hand.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 270-30 spectrometer, electronic spectra on a Hitachi U2000 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a AEI MS30 instrument.

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-methyl acetate (1a) : A mixture of 5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-acetic acid¹² (100 mmol) in excess methanol and few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were refluxed for 4–6 h. Excess methanol was then distilled off and the ester formed was extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was washed with bicarbonate solution, water, and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Benzene was then removed by distillation to yield the product (85%), b.p. 164–68° (0.8 mm Hg) ($\eta^{29} = 1.5280$); λ_{\max} 288, 231 nm;

ν_{\max} 2950, 1736, 1605, 1500, 1320, 1260, 1220, 1170, 1090 cm^{-1} ; m/z 250 (M^+), 236, 178, 147.

Other compounds were similarly prepared: **1b** (88%), b.p. 119–21° (0.5 mm Hg); **c** (79%), 115–16°; **d** (82%), 188–92° (0.5 mm Hg); **e** (86%), 178–82° (1–2 mm Hg); **f** (90%), 144–45° (0.3 mm Hg); **g** (92%), 98–101° (1–3 mm Hg).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-acetylhydrazide (2a): A mixture of **1a** (100 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (150 mmol) in 1-propanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol, (73%), m.p. 120–22° (Found: N, 11.52. Required: N, 11.2%); λ_{\max} 285.5 nm; ν_{\max} 3307, 2938, 1634, 1506 cm^{-1} ; m/z 250 (M^+), 219, 191, 177, 146.

Other compounds were similarly prepared: **2b** (76%), m.p. 92–94°; **c** (71%), >250°; **d** (72%), >250°; **e** (78%), 63–65°; **f** (77%), 152–55°; **g** (75%), 84–86°.

5-[5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-yl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-(3H)-thione (3a): To a cooled (0°) solution of **2a** (7.56 mmol) in methanol (30 ml), CS_2 (17.64 mmol) was added followed by KOH (8.06 mmol). The solution was refluxed on a steam-bath for 9 h and then cooled to room temperature overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the residue dissolved in ice-water. The resulting solution was filtered and the filtrate was acidified with 1N HCl and the solid obtained was extracted with a 1 : 1 mixture of ether and ethyl acetate. The organic layer was then dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by chromatography, eluting with hexane-ethyl acetate (2 : 1) (68%), m.p. 150–52° (Found: N, 9.61. Required: N, 9.59%); λ_{\max} 261.0, 208.5 nm; ν_{\max} 3240, 2933, 1614, 1560, 1063, 744 cm^{-1} ; m/z 292 (M^+), 191, 177, 146, 131, 115, 91.

Other compounds were synthesised by following similar procedure: **3b** (59%), m.p. 78–80°; λ_{\max} 267, 203 nm; ν_{\max} 3071, 2937, 1617, 1491, 1171, 1051, 755 cm^{-1} ; **c** (52%), 208–10°; λ_{\max} 268, 230 nm; ν_{\max} 3421, 2935, 1594, 1498, 1051, 711 cm^{-1} ; **d** (55%), 182–86°; λ_{\max} 269, 230 nm; ν_{\max} 3152, 1594, 1489, 1053, 706 cm^{-1} ; **e** (64%), 140–43°; λ_{\max} 328.5, 209.5, 259.0 nm; ν_{\max} 3061, 1681, 1617, 1502, 1451, 1051, 714 cm^{-1} ; **f** (70%), 168–70°; λ_{\max}

261.0, 221.0 nm; ν_{\max} 3092, 2953, 1616, 1508, 1058, 740 cm^{-1} ; **g** (72%), 118–20°; λ_{\max} 250.0, 213.5 nm; ν_{\max} 3360, 3168, 1614, 1490, 1047, 728 cm^{-1} .

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